

Assessing conservation agents in archaeological wood by neutron imaging

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Abstract

Archaeological wooden artefacts are commonly found in waterlogged conditions exhibiting a degraded and fragile wood structure. Depending on the degree of degradation, they might collapse and/or shrink during drying processes after excavation, leading to a total loss of the cultural heritage information encoded in the wood structure. Conservation treatments are thus required to prevent damage and to bring the samples into a chemically and physically stable condition. However, the distribution of conservation agents might impact the conservation quality, impairing the analysis of the sample. Relevant information of the internal anatomical wood structure and its interaction with impregnated conservation agents can be obtained in a non-destructive manner using imaging-based techniques, such as X-ray and Neutron computed tomography. In this work, neutron computed tomography (N-CT) has been used to study the penetration behaviour of different conservation agents using

alcohol-ether resin (AlEt), saccharose (Sac), silicone oil (Sil) and polyethylene glycol with different treatments, PEG (1), PEG(2) and PEG(3), in archaeological wood samples exhibiting different anatomical structures. Fifty-one samples from a reference collection established between 2008 and 2011 covering a wide variety of methods and wood genera were measured with thermal neutrons. Thirteen of them were fully investigated to assess the penetration depth and distribution of the conservation agents inside the samples. The results show that neutrons feature high contrast for Sil, PEG and Sac conservation agents, which display different penetration paths depending on the anatomical wood structure. The AlEt treatment, on the other hand, is barely detected from the measured imaging data.

Keywords: neutron computed tomography, X-ray computed tomography, archaeological wood, conservation

Introduction

The study of wooden archaeological finds can deliver key information in cultural heritage research, for example, the wooden genus used and information about the period of origin, the process of manufacturing and the application of the artefact and its use. Wooden artefacts, however, are commonly found in a degraded condition, i.e., both the cellulose and hemicellulose of wood cells are degraded by the action of soil biota and water, making the wood spongy and weak, which demands an appropriate conservation treatment (Blanchette 2000). The aim of the conservation

is to bring the archaeological wooden artefacts into a chemically and physically stable condition without altering their original microstructure, outer geometry, and appearance. This is achieved by impregnating the samples with conservation agents (e.g., oils, wax, and natural/synthetic resins), which fill the cell wall micro-cavities and/or cell lumina resulting in preventing drying stress. Different conservation methods have been proposed so far employing different combinations of both natural and synthetic polymer materials (www.rgzm.de/kur, 2022).

The analysis of the 3D structure of wood and the assessment of the effectiveness of the conservation methods should be performed while not affecting the integrity of the examined material. Among the possible candidate techniques, both X-ray computed tomography (X-CT) and neutron computed tomography (N-CT) imaging have demonstrated being suitable testing methods for this purpose (de Vetter 2006, Mannes 2008, Osterloh et al. 2008, Stelzner and Million 2015, Stelzner et al. 2022). In both techniques, projections (i.e., radiographs) of the investigated sample recorded at different rotation angles are used to reconstruct the volumetric representation of the sample by using appropriate algorithms thus avoiding the need for physical cutting to inspect the internal structure of the sample and complex sample preparation.

The main differences between both techniques relies on the interaction pattern between the radiation and the sample. However, as the attenuation coefficient of neutrons (i.e., the parameter describing the degree to which a material attenuates the radiation beam) by hydrogen is much larger than for X-ray (Stelzner et al. 2010, Schillinger 2015), all chemical conservation agents, being hydrogen-based materials, have more chance to be observed with N-CT, as more contrast can be achieved. Hence N-CT can be used as a complementary tool to quantify the penetration length and the 3D distribution of conservation agents inside the sample, which is vital to assess the impact of the treatment, and to provide new insights about dynamic processes occurring during the interaction of the conservation agents with the wood matrix.

With the availability of reactors and spallation neutron sources, neutron imaging has been successfully employed to analyse wooden objects. Assessment of the distribution of wood conservation agents and other hydrogen-rich materials were reported by Niemz et al. (2004), Lehmann et al. (2005) and Osterloh et al., (2019). Mannes et al. (2006, 2007, 2009) determined the distribution of moisture and performed tree ring analysis. Derome et al. (2013) studied the role of water in wood. N-CT was also used to determine the impregnation time necessary to conserve archaeological leather with polyethylene glycol (PEG) (Wiesner 2009) and the distribution and concentration of PEG in archaeological wood (Demoulin et al. 2015).

In the present work, thermal N-CT has been applied on fifty-one archaeological wooden samples treated with different conservation treatments. The neutron imaging data is used to assess the conservation methods by observing the penetration and distribution of the conservation agents in the wood matrix.

Materials and methods

Samples

The samples studied in this work belong to a reference collection at the Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany that was built up between 2008-2011. In total, the collection consists of 23 test series with approximately 770 specimens collected from different sites. In this study, samples from the collection were selected in order to cover a wide variety of methods and wood genera. The samples had been conserved with different conservation methods at different institutions (Table 1, www.rgzm.de/kur, 2022). To achieve a high resolution of the conserved wood structure, core samples with a diameter of ~5 mm and a height of ~10 mm, were extracted. This allowed the samples to fit completely in the field of view of the detector chosen for the experiment. The samples were taken in the outer layer because it was assumed that more conservation agent could be detected in that degraded region (Figure 1). For all wood types, a non-conserved air-dried sample from the collection was used as a reference.

Figure 1. Position of the core sample (red point) in the sample.

For the N-CT analyses, the samples were conveniently distributed into 6 aluminium tubes, allocating 8-10 samples per tube. The aluminium container is nearly transparent to neutron radiation and guarantees physical stability of the samples. Therefore, it is ideally suited for the present study.

Table 1. Detailed overview of conservation methods analysed in this study.

Conservation method	Institutions and short descriptions of the methods
Alcohol-ether-resin (AIET)	Institution: Schweizerisches Nationalmuseum, Zürich, Switzerland. Treatment: Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with diethyl ether. Soaking of wood with diethyl ether in resin-diethyl solution. Drying by evaporation of the diethyl ether in the vacuum vessel. Application of surface protection 3 % Paraloid B72 solution in acetone. Impregnation solution: 70.7 % diethyl ether, 16.1 % dammar resin, 6.4 % rosin, 3.2 % dienol D102, 3.2 % rhizinus oil, 0.4 % PEG 400 Number of samples: 8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)
Kauramin 800® (K800)	Institution: Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie, Mainz, Germany Treatment: Bath impregnation at room temperature. Replacement of the solution when early polymerisation occurs. Curing of the impregnated wood in the heating cabinet at 60 °C. Afterwards slow, controlled air-drying. Dip in linseed oil varnish. Impregnation solution: 25 % Kauramin 800 solution (72 L resin + 210 L deionised water, 3.6 L urea, 7.2 L triethylene glycol) Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 2000) one-step and freeze-drying (PEG1)	Institution: Nationalmuseet, Copenhagen, Denmark Treatment: Starting with 10 % PEG 2000 solution. Increasing the concentration up to 40 % at room temperature. Freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C). Removal of excess PEG from the surface with a soft brush and ethanol. Subsequent surface stabilisation with 25 % PEG 2000 solution in ethanol. Impregnation solution: PEG 2000, 10 – 40 % solution with tap water Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400 and 4000) two-step and freeze-drying (PEG2)	Institution: Brandenburgisches Landesamt für Denkmalpflege, Zossen, Germany Treatment: Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 5 % PEG 400 solution. Raising the concentration in 5 % steps. At its calculated final concentration, it was kept constant. Then the increase of PEG 4000 solution was continued in 5 % steps up to its final concentration. Precooling of the wood to 5 °C then deep-freezing to -25 to -35 °C, freeze-drying in cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C). Impregnation solution: PEG-solution in demineralised water (PEG 400 and PEG 4000) was adapted according to the condition of the wood (PEGcon) Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Polyethylene glycol (PEG 400, 1500 and 4000) three-step and freeze-drying (PEG3)	Institution: Archäologische Staatssammlung, Munich, Germany Treatment: Soaking in demineralised water. Starting with 11 % increasing to 15 % PEG 400 solution at room temperature. 16 % increasing to 20.5 % PEG 1500 solution at 40 °C. 20.5 % increasing to 27.5 % PEG 4000 solution at 40 °C. Washing of the wood and wrapping in cellulose tissues. Intermediate storage in freezer (-25 to -35 °C) until freeze-drying. Subsequent freeze-drying in a cooled chamber (approx. -30 °C). Excess of PEG was removed with a brush and ethanol. Impregnation solution: PEG-solution in demineralised water: 15 % PEG 400, 16-20.5 % PEG 1500, 20.5-27.5 % PEG 4000 Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Saccarose (Sac)	Institution: Sächsisches Landesamt für Archäologie, Dresden, Germany Treatment: Concentrated the solution in 10 % steps, from 10 % up to 60 % sugar solution at room temperature. Slow, controlled air-drying in microperforated bags. Removal of crystallised sugar residues from the surface with damp sponge. Impregnation solution: Aqueous sucrose solution 10 % – 60 %. If necessary biocide addition composed of 0.6 %, sodium benzoate (E211), 0.5 % Parmetol K40, 0.5 % Quartasept Plus and 0.02 % Tallofin OT Number of samples: 10 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (3), pine, spruce)
Silicone oil (Sil)	Institution: Texas University, Texas, USA Treatment: Exchange of water with ethanol. Exchange of ethanol with acetone. Placing the still dripping wet acetone-impregnated samples in impregnation solution under normal atmospheric conditions. Triggering the polymerisation of the impregnation solution by gaseous catalyst: DBTDA (dibutyl diacetate). Impregnation solution: 80 % silicone oil (SFD1 (66 %) + SFD5 (34 %) - silanol functional polydimethylsiloxanes "PDMS") and 20 % crosslinker MTMS (methyltrimethoxysilane) Number of samples: 8 (alder, ash, beech, fir (2), oak (2), pine)

Neutron computed tomography

An N-CT experiment was performed at measuring position no.2 of the SINQ thermal neutron beamline, NEUTRA at the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI). During the experiment, a total of six measurements (one measurement per tube) were performed taking approximately eight hours each. For each measurement, a total of 226 projections with exposure

time of 25 seconds each were obtained during the sample rotation and recorded with a 2048x2048 charge-coupled device (CCD) camera detector. The sample detector distance was ~12 mm and the field of view of the setup was 77.1 × 77.1 mm² with voxel size of 37.67 µm. Scattering and systematic bias related artifacts were attenuated using the experimental black body correction approach. The tomographic reconstruction was performed using the

Figure 2. Cross-sections from the reconstructed N-CT data of the measured samples. Each column represents the result obtained for one of the six N-CT measurements.

MuhRec and the Octopus softwares (Dierick et al. 2004, Kaestner 2011).

Results and discussion

Preliminary results of the analyses discussed here show differences between both conservation agents and wood genus. Figure 2 provides a general overview of the results, showing cross-sections from the reconstructed N-CT imaging data for all measured samples. The images indicate the presence of conservation agents, which can be seen as grayscale gradients whose strength and distribution vary with the wood type. Several vessels of different sizes in the oak (*Quercus* spp.) samples can be clearly distinguished too. For the purpose of this study, two test series listed in Table 2 with different anatomic structures and where the largest number of conservation methods are available were selected and examined in this work.

Looking at the three-dimensional (3D) reconstructions of the N-CT data, relevant information about the penetration of the conservation agent can be obtained. Figure 3 shows

Figure 3. Cross-sections and 3D rendering of pine (*Pinus* spp.) samples, dried (no conservation agent) and impregnated with silicone oil and PEG(2) products. The difference in attenuation coefficients between the wood matrix and the conservation agents allows a clear identification of the agent. Silicone oil fills thin layers along and across the vertical direction. The PEG(2) product spreads over wide regions along the whole sample instead.

Table 2. Overview of the analysed core samples. Each row in the table corresponds to each analysed sample whose 3D renderings are shown in Figures 3-5.
¹ Mean value of the sample series.

Sample	KUR-No.	Genus	Conservation method	Umax (%)	Condition (de Jong)	Basic density (g/cm ³)	Residual basic density (%)
Pi1-Air	V03-01	pine	Air dried	390	2	0.219	52
Pi1-AIEt	V03-17	pine	Alcohol-Ether	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Pi1-PEG1	V03-35	pine	PEG (1)	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Pi1-PEG2	V03-32	pine	PEG (2)	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Pi1-PEG3	V03-20	pine	PEG (3)	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Pi1-Sac	V03-45	pine	Saccharose	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Pi1-Sil	V03-42	pine	Silicone oil	332 ¹	2	0.251 ¹	60 ¹
Oa2-Air	V16-15	oak	Air dried	362	2	0.233	42
Oa2-AIEt	V16-09	oak	Alcohol-Ether	175	3	0.414	74
Oa2-PEG1	V16-18	oak	PEG (1)	189	2	0.391	70
Oa2-PEG3	V16-36	oak	PEG (3)	188	2	0.393	70
Oa2-Sac	V16-17	oak	Saccharose	184	3	0.399	71
Oa2-Sil	V16-13	oak	Silicone oil	187	2	0.394	70

how PEG(2) and silicone oil impregnate the wooden structure of a highly degraded pine (*Pinus* spp.) sample. As can be seen in the figure, the presence of the conservation agent can be detected by a simple comparison of the impregnated samples with the reference, dried sample. The conservation agents appear to occupy regions characterised by the lightest greyscale values, whereas the unimpregnated wood is identified as regions having darker greyscale values. This can be understood by the high affinity for neutron attenuation of the atoms forming the conservation agent, which results in higher attenuation coefficients for them. It can also be seen from the figure, that the penetration front of silicone oil is different to the one from PEG(2). While silicone oil is located especially along late wood fibers and probably in the rays, PEG(2) spreads over wider regions in the early wood vessels (see arrows in Figure 3).

A similar analysis was performed for other impregnation products in both pine and oak samples. Figures 4 and 5 respectively illustrate 3D renderings obtained for pine and oak samples, impregnated with alcohol-ether-resin (AIEt), saccharose, polyethylene glycol (PEG(3) and PEG(1)) and silicone oil (see Table 1 for details). It can be seen from Figures 4 and 5 that silicone oil, PEG(1), and PEG(3) can be easily detected by N-CT, since regions of the samples filled by them display different attenuation of neutron radiation with respect to the non-impregnated wood matrix, which is characterised by darker grey scale values. Especially the

Figure 4. Cross-sections and 3D rendering of pine (*Pinus* spp.) samples dried and impregnated with alcohol-ether-resin, saccharose, PEG(3), PEG(1) and silicone oil products.

Figure 5. Cross-sections and 3D rendering of oak (*Quercus* spp.) samples dried and impregnated with alcohol-ether-resin, saccharose, PEG(3), PEG(1) and silicone oil products.

structure of PEG (1) impregnated wood shows very low contrast which is interpreted for an even distribution of the PEG. The saccharose treated samples display a higher

contrast due to a higher attenuation of neutron radiation in the late wood region. This indicates that saccharose is predominantly deposited in these latewood cells. This does not occur for AIEt which is hard to identify when comparing the respective impregnated samples with the corresponding dried reference sample. The use of larger amounts of resin in the AIEt and saccharose combined neutrons with lower energies (i.e., cold neutrons) could potentially enhance the contrast for those conservation agents and thus facilitate their detection using N-CT.

It should also be noted that the conservation agents silicone oil, PEG(1) and PEG(3) follow a similar penetration pattern filling thin layers along and across the axial direction, as that observed in pine for silicone oil (Figure 4). In particular, the layers running along the axial direction in the latewood seems to be highly favourable for the penetration. Those regions might be occupied by resin channels in the late wood and wood rays lying along and perpendicular to the axial direction, respectively. This make sense, as a typical feature of pine are the large window pits connecting the radial wood ray cells to the axial tracheids. It is also noteworthy that for the oak samples the conservation agent chose different pathways to flow than the one offered by the large vessels, which appear to be empty (or filled with other low neutron-absorbing substances) in most cases. The oak vessels might be blocked by the so-called tyloses, i.e., baggy cell protuberances which are formed by the plant to block the vessels. The tyloses have relatively thin membranes which are most likely too thin to be detected with the used experimental setup (De Micco et al. 2016).

The described results strongly indicate that the conservation agents detected by N-CT penetrate into the degraded structure of the wood matrix. The mode of accumulation depends on the conservation agent and the anatomical structure of the wood. It is interesting to note here that the amount of conservation agent absorbed into the wood structure cannot be related to good volume stabilisation. For example, silicone oil fills many parts of the lumina, but the entire sample has comparatively high shrinkage (Stelzner et al. 2022). However, further studies and higher resolutions are needed to investigate the penetration of the conservation agent into the cell walls, which is crucial for the conservation of better preserved woods (Pedersen 2015).

Conclusions and outlook

Neutron computed tomography has proved to be a powerful technique to study the penetration and distribution of different conservation agents in conserved archaeological wooden samples. This technique allows investigation of the internal wood structure in a non-destructive manner and does not require difficult sample preparation.

These preliminary results shows that the conservation agents silicone oil, PEG(1) and PEG(3) preferably fill the thin layers through the whole sample. The combined use of N-CT and X-CT experiments with higher spatial resolution would be required to provide a more refined information in this regard. In the case of pine, the PEG(2) agent was found to be spread out over wider regions. In contrast to that, the AIEt conservation agents display a weak contrast and can barely be detected in the measured imaging data. The highest image contrast was achieved by silicone oil.

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